

NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF PROGRESSIVE FAILURE OF BOLTED SINGLE-LAP JOINTS OF WOVEN REINFORCED COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Numerical modelling of progressive failure of bolted joints of composite is still challenging, material nonlinearity and multiple contact surfaces could lead to convergence issue when implicit finite element (FE) analysis is performed. In this study, the progressive failure of a single-lap bolted joint of woven reinforced composite is investigated both experimentally and numerically. The explicit FE analysis available in Abaqus commercial software is employed due to its robustness on treating multiple contact surfaces. In the FE model, three dimensional (3D) shell elements are used for the plies and cohesive elements are used for the material interfaces to capture delamination. Material nonlinearity due to fibre rupture, matrix cracking and micro cracking are represented by proper material degradation model. A set of experiments was conducted to validate the FE analysis. Digital image correlation (DIC) was used to observe the out-of-plane displacement around the bolt hole of the specimens during testing.

1 INTRODUCTION

Bolted joints of woven fabric reinforced composites are widely used in aerospace structures under severe environmental conditions [1]. The study of progressive failure is important and of particular interests. The bearing failure mode of bolted joint which gives highest strength and is less catastrophic is preferred [2, 3]. Numerical simulation for the progressive damage and failure behaviour of bolted joints by means of finite element method (FEM) may provide a better understanding. Xiao and Ishikawa developed a two dimensional (2D) progressive damage model to predict mechanical behavior of composite joint [4, 5]. McCarthy et. al., developed a FE model to study the effect of bolt hole clearance in bolted joints [6, 7]. Zhou et al., investigated the use of a progressive damage model on a 2D plain weave composite [8]. Ansar et al., reviewed the modeling strategies for 3D woven composites [9].

The existing numerical models for bolted joints [5, 6, 7, 8] mainly focus on damage onset, and modeling the whole failure process considering material response with significant bearing failure remains challenging. Capturing significant material failure was found to be not practical in implicit FE modelling due to convergence issue [10, 11, 12]. The difficulties are mainly resulted from two reasons, i.e., the complex contact geometries involved and, the material nonlinearities due to fiber and matrix failure as well as delamination.

In this study, an explicit FE analysis model is presented for simulating bolted single-lap joint of woven composite. The FE model is built using 3D shell elements for each composite ply and cohesive elements (CEs) for the material interface in between the plies. The material nonlinearities due to fiber

rupture, matrix micro-cracking and plasticity effects can be accounted for by proper material damage model. A set of experiments following the ASTM D5961/D5961M-13 standard test protocol [13] for bearing response of polymer matrix composite laminates has been conducted to validate the explicit FE model. The digital image correlation (DIC) was used to measure the out-of-plane displacement around the bolted area during testing.

2 MATERIAL DEGRADATION MODEL

The woven composite ply is modeled as a homogeneous orthotropic elastic material but with the capability to sustain progressive damage of material stiffness. Material nonlinearities within plies, i.e., fiber rupture, matrix cracking and inelastic effects due to micro-matrix cracking are accounted for by appropriate constitutive law which is defined as follows

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{22} \\ \varepsilon_{12}^{el} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{(1-d_1)E_1} & \frac{-\nu_{12}}{E_1} & 0 \\ \frac{-\nu_{21}}{E_2} & \frac{1}{(1-d_2)E_2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{(1-d_{12})2G_{12}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where d_1 and d_2 are damage variables associated with the fiber damage along 1 and 2 directions, respectively, whilst d_{12} is the damage variable related to matrix damage due to shear deformation. In the plane stress case required to characterize the plane properties of woven fabric composite plies, ε_{11} , ε_{22} and ε_{12}^{el} are elastic strain components and σ_{11} , σ_{22} and σ_{12} are stress components. Plastic strain ε_{12}^{pl} is considered for shear deformation. E_1 and E_2 are Young's moduli in the principle directions, ν_{12} and ν_{21} are Poisson's ratios, and G_{12} is the in plane shear modulus. Two main failure mechanisms for fabric reinforced composite plies have been considered in the damage mode i.e., fiber dominated failure in tension or compression in the two principle directions; and matrix dominated failure in in-plane shear. And these two failure mechanisms are assumed to be decoupled with each other. This model has been implemented in Abaqus/Explicit FE package through the VUMAT users' subroutine (ABQ_PLY_FABRIC)[14].

3 EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

The tests were performed following the ASTM D5961/D5961M-13 standard test method for bearing response of polymer matrix composite laminates[13]. The procedure B (single-shear tensile or compressive loading of a two-piece specimen) of this test method was used in this study because it has been extensively used for developing design allowable data. In our study, five specimens were tested and the layup sequence of the laminate is [0, 45, 45, 0]2s. The tests were conducted using INSTRON 8501 universal testing machine equipped with a 100 kN load cell. The cross head speed of the machine was 2mm/min. Besides, the 3D DIC system was utilized to experimentally study progressive damage of the specimens by measuring the out-of-plane displacement of the joints.

Fig.1. The test setup for the bearing test using a 3D DIC technique: (A) two CCD cameras with a 35mm lens, (B) LED white light source, (C) composite single-lap bolt joint speckled with acrylic paint, a zoom in view is provided on the right

4 FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

Fig.2. Configuration of the bolted single-lap joint of woven composite and the FE mesh

The FE mesh as well as the boundary conditions of the bolted single-lap joint of woven composite is shown in Fig.2. The model is built in three regions, i.e. regions I, II and III, different mesh strategies are used in these regions. In the region I, the mesh is based on the classic laminate theory (CLT). The region II is built in mesoscale, each ply is modeled with 3D shell elements and the interfaces in between adjacent plies are discretised by using the cohesive elements (CEs) to account for delamination. In this region, composite material can not sustain damage. In the region III, the model is also built in mesoscale but with refined mesh. The material degradation model defined in Eq.(1) is used in this region to capture material damage and the consequent failure. Element deletion technique has been employed in this region to overcome numerical issue.

Fig.3. Illustration of the contact pairs used in the FE model.

The interaction between the bolt and composite is of crucial importance for the modeling accuracy. The contact pairs used in this study are illustrated in Fig.3. The bolt is more rigid and hence it is chosen to be the master surface and the composite is the slave surface. For the region considering material damage, the elements with material failure due to the contact with bolt could be deleted from the model and the contact surfaces must be updated. For this reason, the general contact algorithm in Abaqus is adopted to account for the new exposed element surfaces. Specially, the interaction among the plies must also be considered when the CEs are deleted due to delamination. For the material far away from the bolt, the surface to surface contact algorithm is used to eliminate unnecessary computational efforts.

5 RESULTS

The evolution of the bolted joint's deformation from the simulation and the final deformation observed from the tested specimen are shown in Fig.4. With the increasing of the external loading, it is observed that the bolt tilts and eventually sinks into the composite material.

Fig.4. Comparison of the overall deformation of the joint between experimental observation and simulation results.

Fig.5. Out-of-plane displacement (w) field around the bolted area (left), DIC reading (top right) and the simulation result (bottom right).

Due to the eccentric tensile load path, the secondary bending is resulted in for the single lap bolt joints. The out-of-plane deformation around the bolt hole recorded by the DIC is shown in Fig.5, in

which the simulation result is also provided. It is shown that the predicted result is in good agreement with the experimental observation.

Fig.6. Load displacement curve of the bolted joint of woven composite

The load displacement curves of the specimen is shown in Fig.6. In general, each curve starts with a linear portion. Subsequently, the initiation of damage (marked as point “A”) activates a nonlinear part of the curve. In this region, the joint can still carry the external loading until reaching point “B”. The load then starts to drop which is accompanied with significant bearing failure until final failure of the bolted joint (point “C”).

6 CONCLUSION

The progressive failure of bolted joint of woven composite is investigated numerically and experimentally. The explicit finite element (FE) analysis in Abaqus is employed due to its advantages in treating complex contact geometries. Material failure due to the contact with bolt was observed in both the tested specimen and the modeling results. The out-of-plane displacement around the bolted area is compared with the digital image correlation (DIC) reading which was taken during testing. The present study provides a numerical tool for the modelling of the progressive failure of bolted joint of woven composite.

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